

PROPLANET

Enhanced Safe and Sustainable
coatings for supporting the Planet

NEWSLETTER

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UPDATES ON REGULATIONS IMPROVING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF PRODUCTS

Starting from 12 January 2026, all EU Member States were required to monitor and control PFAS levels in drinking water in accordance with the updated standards set out in Directive (EU) 2020/2184 on the quality of water intended for human consumption.

These provisions introduce harmonised monitoring requirements across the European Union and strengthen the protection of public health from per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), a group of persistent chemicals of increasing regulatory concern.

New PFAS limits introduced by the Directive include:

- Sum of 20 PFAS (C4–C13): 0.10 µg/L
- Total PFAS: 0.50 µg/L

These limits require Member States to implement appropriate analytical methods and monitoring programmes to ensure compliance with the new drinking water quality standards.

For further information, consult the official resources below:

Directive (EU) on the quality of water intended for human consumption

Technical Guidelines for PFAS Analysis in Drinking Water

Moreover, regulation (EU) 2024/1781 establishes a comprehensive framework for setting ecodesign requirements aimed at improving the sustainability, durability, and circularity of products placed on the EU market. It replaces Directive 2009/125/EC and updates existing legislation to support the EU's transition toward a climate-neutral, resource-efficient economy under the European Green Deal.

Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)

OUR SSBD WORKSHOPS IDENER AND PROPLANET AT THE SSBD WORKSHOP IN BRUSSELS

On **March 19th 2026**, PROPLANET attended the **6th Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Stakeholder Event**, “Safe and Sustainable by Design – Accelerating the Industrial Transition,” in Brussels. During this event industry leaders, policymakers, researchers, and innovators gathered to discuss the revised SSbD Framework and its role in driving Europe’s industrial transformation. The conference provided a valuable platform for PROPLANET to engage with the wider SSbD community, explore insights from **Horizon Europe projects**, and follow discussions on opportunities and challenges related to wider SSbD adoption at regional and national levels. The event also highlighted upcoming EU Innovation and Substitution Hubs aimed at supporting companies—especially SMEs—in developing, testing, and scaling SSbD innovations.

On **20 March 2026**, [a dedicated meeting for Safe and Sustainable by Design \(SSbD\) projects](#) took place in Brussels. The meeting was hosted at the **Albert Borschette Conference Centre** and brought together representatives from projects funded under several SSbD-related Horizon Europe topics.

The day began with a short introduction by the **European Commission**, setting the context for discussions and highlighting ongoing policy developments in safe and sustainable chemicals and materials. Participants then engaged in **parallel breakout sessions**, where projects presented their work and exchanged ideas on opportunities for **future collaboration and knowledge sharing**. European Commission colleagues working in the corresponding policy areas joined these sessions, contributing to the discussions and providing policy perspectives.

The meeting concluded with a **plenary session**, during which participants reflected on **good practices identified during the discussions** and explored potential avenues for **future cooperation among projects**.

The event primarily brought together projects funded under topics related to the development and assessment of **safe and sustainable by design chemicals, materials, coatings, polymers, nanomaterials, and bio-based alternatives**, as well as projects focusing on **innovative assessment methods, computational modelling, and advanced characterisation approaches**. **IDENER**, our project coordinator was there to provide insights from our PROPLANET as well, though an insightful presentation.

ACCELERATING THE INDUSTRIAL TRANSITION

SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN 6TH STAKEHOLDERS CONFERENCE

19 March 2026

Brussels | Online

SSbD «IN PRACTICE» WORKSHOP IN ATHENS

20 April 2026

T.1: SSbD Framework, Policy & Regulatory Readiness

T.2: Industrial Success Stories & Real-World Impact

T.3: R&D challenges in SSbD implementation

ZEUS WYNDHAM GRAND ATHENS - GREECE | 9.00-13.00 EEST | Zeus Conference Room

The workshop “SSbD in Practice: Current Status, Critical Barriers and Success Cases”, was held on 20 April 2026 at the ZEUS Wyndham Grand Athens, organised as a key satellite event leading into COATINGS 2026. The workshop gathered more than 140 registered participants, both on site and online. Designed to set the stage for the discussions to follow during the main conference, the workshop brought together industry representatives, researchers, and policymakers to explore how Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principles are being applied in real-world settings.

Through focused thematic sessions, expert presentations, and interactive discussions, the event offered participants a deep dive into policy readiness, industrial successes, and R&D challenges—providing a timely and relevant knowledge foundation just ahead of the COATINGS 2026 sessions.

The thematic areas are summarised below:

- Thematic 1: **SSbD Framework, Policy & Regulatory Readiness**
- Thematic 2: **Industrial Success Stories & Real World Impact**
- Thematic 3: **R&D challenges in SSbD implementation**

The workshop opened with remarks from **Mr. Alexandros Katroutzos**, President of the Hellenic Association of Chemical Industries (HACI) and CEO of **NEOTEX S.A.**, followed by a series of important presentations, including those of **Dr Georgios Katalagarianakis** (Ex- EC officer), **Prof. Eugenia Valsami Jones** (University of Birmingham) and **Dr Apostolos Scarlatos**.

Industry representatives, included **Dr Marina Sofra** – R&D Manager (VITEX S.A.), **Dr Maddalena Rostagno** – CEO (DG Advanced), **Dr Stavros Moschidis** – Regulatory Affairs Manager (ISOMAT), **Dr Aris Gorgias** – QHSE Manager (Megara Resins Group), **Dr Emanuele Grillo** – (TecnochimicaS.p.A.), and **Dr Electra Papadopoulou** – Senior Researcher (CHIMAR). All presenters offered the audience of the event a unique opportunity to gain high level insights into cutting edge SSbD approaches and their practical application across research and industry. Finally, project coordinators and representatives took the stage to highlight the project outcomes and challenges, while they participated in roundtable discussions.

PROPLANET contributed to **Thematic 3** by presenting its work on advancing Safe and Sustainable by Design methodologies within real-world research and innovation settings. In this session other relevant projects shared the stage in a panel discussion (including IRISS, BIO-SUSHY, MOZART, NICKEFFECT, SAFARi, FreeMe and TORNADO).

During its session, PROPLANET highlighted practical challenges encountered in translating SSbD principles into applied industrial and research processes, while showcasing methodological solutions developed through its project activities. By participating in the short presentations and subsequent panel discussion, PROPLANET added valuable insights to the dialogue on the rising key barriers to replacing PFAS-based coatings with SSbD alternatives in real market conditions, reinforcing the project's role in supporting Europe's transition toward safer and more sustainable innovation pathways.

More information can be found [HERE!](#)

You may also access the recording [HERE!](#)

4TH STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT EVENT

The 4th PROPLANET Project Streaming Event was successfully held online, under the lead of HOLOSS, on March 5th 2026, bringing together participants for an engaging programme of presentations, newly released infographic videos, and a round table discussion focused on **“PFAS-Free by Design: Advancing SSbD for a Safer Tomorrow.”**

The event featured 8 insightful presentations highlighting the project's progress, alongside the premiere of three new infographic videos presenting key aspects of the PROPLANET approach. A central highlight of the programme was the round table discussion titled **“The Impact of PFAS on Society and the Environment – and the Alternatives Ahead.”**

During the discussion, experts examined the **societal and environmental challenges associated with per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)** and explored the need to transition toward safer chemical solutions. The session also presented **PFAS-free alternatives developed within the PROPLANET Project** and discussed how the **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework** can support innovation and guide industries toward safer and more sustainable materials and processes.

The event provided an opportunity for participants to exchange perspectives on **PFAS-free innovation and the role of SSbD in shaping a safer and more sustainable future.** We also had the honor to have our project officer with us during the call who gave a warm welcome to the participants.

The agenda can be found here:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/PROPLANET-4th-Streaming-Event-Agenda.pdf>

You may access the newly released videos on the PROPLANET YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/@PROPLANETProject>

Safety - Tiered approach for hazard assessment

- Define Safety Criteria for the novel coatings**
 - ✓ No CMR chemicals (carcinogenic, mutagenic, or reprotoxic)
 - ✓ Equal or improved performance for selected endpoints
- Data Mining & analysis**

Retrieve available data for individual chemicals, exclude CMR
- Data gap filling**

In Silico Modeling- NOVAM's in-house mutagenicity models
- In Vitro Testing- Testing of the formulations**

Carcinogenicity, Mutagenicity, Repro-toxicity (CMR) in the formulations

Replace

Formulations

In vitro models

Endpoints

- Cytotoxicity
- Genotoxicity
- Mutagenicity
- Carcinogenicity
- Repro-toxicity
- ROS
- Inflammation
- Endocrine disrupting activity

40

PROPLANET FEATURED AT CORDIS

PROPLANET WAS FEATURED ALONGSIDE TEN OTHER HORIZON FUNDED SISTER PROJECTS IN THE CORDIS RESULTS PACK ON “SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN (SSbD) CHEMICALS AND MATERIALS FOR EUROPE’S GREEN TRANSITION.”

This collection highlights EU initiatives driving the shift toward a circular economy through safer, non toxic, sustainable and recyclable chemicals and materials that maintain or improve performance. As the Results Pack explains, meeting Europe’s environmental and sustainability goals requires large scale innovation in advanced materials, supported by the SSbD framework, which guides researchers and industry in minimising impacts across the full life cycle of products. By showcasing 11 leading projects, the Pack underscores the EU’s commitment to strengthening resilience, competitiveness and sustainability across sectors such as textiles, automotive, energy and advanced manufacturing.

Within this broader context, CORDIS placed particular emphasis on PROPLANET’s contribution to “Creating sustainable coatings that protect products and the environment” while reducing environmental and health risks. The article highlights how PROPLANET researchers created a new generation of coatings for the **textile, food packaging and glass sectors**, designed to avoid common ecological and toxicological concerns while delivering high performance—aligning fully with SSbD principles. These innovations aim to support safer value chains, reduce reliance on harmful substances and enable more circular product lifecycles, reinforcing Europe’s transition toward a greener and more sustainable materials industry.

PROPLANET CELEBRATING THE INTERNATIONAL DAY OF WOMEN AND GIRLS IN SCIENCE

On 11 February – International Day of Women and Girls in Science, the PROPLANET Project celebrated the extraordinary contributions of women whose ideas, discoveries, and inventions helped shape our world. Many of these achievements were historically overshadowed or under recognised due to the **Matilda Effect**, a long standing bias that has often minimised the role of women in science.

To honour these pioneers and raise awareness of their impact, PROPLANET produced a special **Matilda Effect booklet**. This publication highlighted the stories of remarkable women scientists — from chemistry and materials science to environmental research and engineering — whose work has driven innovation but whose names may not always be widely known. Through engaging profiles, illustrations, and accessible explanations, the booklet invited readers to discover how these women contributed to breakthroughs that influence our lives today.

Designed to **inspire young readers and the general public alike**, the booklet aimed to encourage curiosity, celebrate diversity, and emphasise the importance of equity in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). The Matilda Effect booklet was made freely available for download, offering educators, families, and science enthusiasts a valuable resource to learn about and celebrate the achievements of women in science.

Read the booklet here:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/02/PROPLANET-Booklet-Matilda-Effect.pdf>

UPDATES FROM THE PROPLANET

THE PROPLANET REPLICATION TOOL IS RELEASED

The **PROPLANET Replication Tool** has recently reached an important milestone with the launch of its **beta version**, marking a significant step forward in supporting the transition toward **PFAS-free coatings and safer material design**.

Developed within the PROPLANET project, the digital platform supports **data-driven decision-making throughout the coating development process**, helping researchers, developers, and industry stakeholders analyse materials and optimise coating formulations. The tool integrates several modelling and analysis components developed by project partners (IDENER, Nova Mchanics, University of Malaga, NILU, RINA and Tecnalia), enabling a comprehensive and collaborative approach to coating innovation.

The Replication Tool brings together multiple functionalities, including **materials management and analysis, first-principle simulations for predicting coating performance, environmental fate modelling, formulation optimisation, and toxicity estimation modules**. These features allow users to evaluate coating properties, assess potential environmental impacts, and identify safer design solutions aligned with the **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)** framework.

In addition to supporting research activities, the tool plays an important role in **facilitating the replication and broader adoption of PROPLANET innovations across different industrial sectors**. By applying advanced algorithms and

optimisation methods, it enables stakeholders to explore how PFAS-free coatings can be adapted to various applications, while maintaining performance, safety, and sustainability.

You may access the Replication Tool through the following link:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/replication-tool/>

PROPLANET PRESS RELEASE ON THE TOOL

A new press release was designed to announce the launch of the PROPLANET Free Replication Tool, a fully open-source, web-based platform designed to guide manufacturers, researchers, and policymakers toward PFAS-free coating solutions for glass, metal, and textiles.

Read the full press release:

https://www.proplanet-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/PROPLANET_Third-PR.pdf

INTERNATION COOPERATION

The PROPLANET project actively addressed international cooperation to maximise its impact by integrating expertise beyond the EU. In this context, Pilkington (PLK), a UK based consortium partner and subsidiary of the globally recognised NSG Group, contributed its extensive expertise in glass production and treatment. NSG Group's strong international presence, broad industrial portfolio, and commitment to innovation aligned closely with PROPLANET's objectives and reinforced the project's global dimension.

International visibility was further enhanced through dissemination activities within NSG's global network, including a LinkedIn post shared with a large professional audience and internal dissemination via NSG's Viva Engage platform, significantly extending awareness of PROPLANET activities. In addition, the consortium participated in international conferences, networking sessions, and B2B meetings to strengthen collaboration, exchange knowledge, and explore new opportunities.

ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

PROPLANET PROJECT AT ECOSYSTEMX INSIGHTS SERIES #18

(14 NOVEMBER 2025, ONLINE)

The PROPLANET Project was recently presented at the ECOSYSTEMX Insights Series #18 Webinar, held on 14 November from 10:00 to 11:30 CET. Representatives from AITEX and Kemijski inštitut – National Institute of Chemistry shared the latest developments of the project, highlighting its work on PFAS-free, safe, and sustainable coatings with applications in textiles, food packaging, and glass.

The session also featured presentations from PROPLANET's sister project, ZeroF, as well as the Ellie.Connect and Re-gioGreenTex platforms, showcasing a broad ecosystem of initiatives advancing sustainable material solutions.

A special thank you was extended to ECOSYSTEMX for providing the opportunity to share PROPLANET's vision and progress.

View the agenda here: <https://lnkd.in/eZrCx-MJ>

21ST GLOBAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE MANUFACTURING (GCSM)

(11 SEPTEMBER 2025, ITALY)

HOLOSS, represented by José Caetano, presented the latest research conducted within the PROPLANET Project during the 21st Global Conference on Sustainable Manufacturing. The presentation, titled “Hazard and Life Cycle Assessment of Safe and Sustainable Coatings,” showcased innovative approaches to evaluating the safety and sustainability of coatings across various applications.

The work highlighted how data-driven assessments and life cycle analysis can support safer and more sustainable manufacturing practices, contributing to a greener future for the coatings industry.

For more information about the event Check here:

<https://gcsmeu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7381598812470960129>

HOLOSS at the 21st GLOBAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE MANUFACTURING – GCSM
11th September, 2025, Bologna, Italy

JRC SSbD bootcamp
Ispra, Italy, 28-30 October 2025

SAFETY AND SUSTAINABILITY BY DESIGN (SSbD) WORKSHOP (28 OCTOBER 2025, ONLINE)

The PROPLANET Project was represented at the Safety and Sustainability by Design (SSbD) Workshop hosted by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) on 28 October. Project partners Kemijski inštitut – National Institute of Chemistry, IDENER, and NILU presented PROPLANET's latest developments, highlighting the application of AI and computational modeling in the design of safe and sustainable coatings for textiles, food packaging, and glass. The presentations demonstrated how the project's approaches were fully aligned with SSbD principles and contributed to the goals of a circular economy, emphasising both safety and environmental sustainability in coating development.

sustainability in coating development.

Please find the agenda: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/b01aab61-fe5d-4e67-906f-ad4ea4b92048_en?filename=SSbD%20boot%20camp-programme%202025%20updated.pdf

Read more here:

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/events/upcoming-events/third-safe-and-sustainable-design-boot-camp-2025-10-28_en

EXELISIS at the Researchers' Night 2025
National Technical University of Athens
26/09/25, Athens, Greece

EXELISIS AT THE RESEARCHERS' NIGHT 2025

(26 SEPTEMBER 2025, ATHENS, GREECE)

EXELISIS IKE, represented the PROPLANET Project, while participating in the Researchers' Night 2025, held at the National Technical University of Athens on 26 September 2025. During the event, the team shared dissemination materials and educational flyers for children, designed to spark curiosity and inspire the next generation of young researchers. Visitors had the opportunity to learn more about sustainable innovation and explore how science can engage younger audiences. The event provided an excellent platform to showcase PROPLANET's mission and foster interest in safe and sustainable materials among students and the public.

More information about the event was made available online: <https://www.ntua.gr/ntuaren/>

PROPLANET MEETINGS

The **PROPLANET Project General Assembly** took place on **21–22 October** in **Lillestrøm, Norway**, hosted by **NILU**. Over two productive days, project partners gathered to **share progress updates, exchange ideas,** and plan the next steps toward developing **PFAS-free, sustainable coatings**.

The meetings were marked by **fruitful discussions, collaboration, and brainstorming sessions**, driving the project closer to its mission of creating **safer and more sustainable materials** for a greener future.

Alongside the assembly, **NILU** and **EXELISIS IKE** hosted a booth to **promote the PROPLANET Project** and highlight the upcoming **COATINGS 2026 Conference**, showcasing innovations in sustainability and surface coatings.

A special thank you was extended to **NILU** for their warm welcome and excellent organisation, which made the two-day event both productive and engaging.

PROPLANET General Assembly meeting | NILU premises
Lillestrøm, Norway, 21-22 October 2025

PROPLANET MEETING IN ATHENS | 19 APRIL 2026 | ATHENS, GREECE

On **19 April 2026**, the PROPLANET consortium convened in Athens in conjunction with the **COATINGS 2026 Conference**, which was held from **20 to 22 April 2026** at the Wyndham Grand Athens.

This meeting represented the final in-person gathering of the consortium before the conclusion of the project and provided an important opportunity for partners to review the overall progress achieved across project activities.

A networking dinner was organised by the project coordinator, **IDENER**, offering an informal and memorable setting for collaboration. The dinner was held at a venue with a panoramic view of the Acropolis of Athens, creating a distinctive atmosphere that encouraged open discussion and strengthened professional relationships among partners.

To ensure continued coordination through the final phase of the project, a final online consortium meeting was scheduled for the following month. This final in-person meeting provided a meaningful moment for the consortium to celebrate the strong collaboration built throughout PROPLANET and to conclude the project with a shared sense of achievement and appreciation for the project completion.

NEW PROPLANET PUBLICATIONS

During this period, the PROPLANET consortium saw significant scientific progress, with nine new publications **accepted and added to the project’s growing open access library**. These additions were announced on both the [PROPLANET project website](#) and [Zenodo](#), expanding the project’s publicly accessible research outputs. With these new entries, the consortium now counts a total of **eleven publications**, covering topics such as PFAS free textile coatings, sustainable biopolymer based materials, innovative nanocellulose membranes, and advanced assessment methods for nano and advanced materials.

NIC: Biobased Hydrophobic Solutions for Natural Textiles—Moving Beyond PFAS

NIC: Eco-Friendly hydrophobic textiles: A shift from PFAs to sustainable bio-polymers

NILU: New Approach Methods (NAMs) for genotoxicity assessment of nano- and advanced materials; Advan-

Nova Mechanics: LungDepo: modelling the regional particle deposition in the human lung via the Enalos Cloud platform

NIC: Sustainable, Safe, and Effective (Super) Hydrophobic Coatings for Cellulosic Fiber Material

NIC: Natural Biopolymer-Based Microcapsules as Sustainable Agents for Hydrophobic Textiles

NIC: Understanding bio-based polymers: A study of origins, properties, biodegradation and their impact on health and the environment

NIC, UMA: Prediction of Hydrophobic Properties in Biopolymer-Based Coatings via Formulation Data Modelling

NIC: FEBS Open Bio – 2025 – Repinc – Understanding bio-based polymers A study of origins properties biodegradation and their

PROPLANET BLOG ARTICLES

NEW BLOG ARTICLE 5: HARNESSING AI AND COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS TO DEVELOP SAFE AND SUSTAIN-ABLE COATINGS

The PROPLANET project demonstrated how digital innovation accelerated the transition toward **safer, PFAS free coating technologies** in its article “Harnessing AI and Computational Tools to Develop Safe and Sustainable Coatings.” By combining artificial intelligence, predictive modelling, and digital simulations, the consortium efficiently evaluated coating performance, safety, and environmental impact across multiple formulations, supporting the identification of high performance PFAS free alternatives for textiles, food packaging, and glass in line with **SSbD principles**. Lifecycle and environmental assessments played a central role, using toxicity prediction and environmental fate modelling to guide material selection and support circular economy objectives. Through data driven design, PROPLANET reduced development time, strengthened decision making, and enabled broader adoption of PFAS free solutions, demonstrating the potential of AI enabled materials innovation to drive safer and more sustainable industrial transformation.

Read the full article:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/harnessing-ai-and-computational-tools-to-develop-safe-and-sustainable-coatings/>

NEW BLOG ARTICLE 6: SUSTAINABLE COATINGS FOR GLASS: ADVANCING PERFORMANCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY

This article marked the sixth blog post published within the PROPLANET project, highlighting advances in sustainable glass coating technologies. Sustainable glass coatings are gaining importance as industries seek high performance solutions that also meet environmental goals. Anti reflective coatings improve light transmission and efficiency in applications such as solar panels and architectural glass, while anti soiling coatings repel water, oils, and particles to maintain performance and reduce cleaning needs.

The PROPLANET project developed **PFAS free hybrid siloxane coatings** combining anti reflective and anti soiling properties through close collaboration between research partners and industry. Designed according to **Safe and Sustainable by Design** principles, these solutions supported greener manufacturing and circular economy practices by delivering durable performance with reduced environmental impact.

Read the full article:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/sustainable-coatings-for-glass-achieving-anti-reflective-and-anti-soiling-properties/>

NEW BLOG ARTICLE 7: REVOLUTIONISING FOOD PACKAGING: HIGH PERFORMANCE BIO-BASED AND HYBRID COATINGS

Sustainable solutions are increasingly important in food packaging as industries seek materials that combine high performance with improved safety and lower environmental impact. Conventional coatings, often based on petroleum derived polymers or PFAS, have raised concerns due to their persistence and limited compatibility with circular economy principles, driving interest in bio based and hybrid alternatives.

The PROPLANET project developed **PFAS free bio based and hybrid coatings** delivering key functionalities such as non stick behaviour, oil and grease resistance, durability, and thermal stability. Developed in line with **Safe and Sustainable by Design** principles, these solutions supported safer materials, improved process efficiency, and more sustainable packaging systems.

Read the full article:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/revolutionising-food-packaging-high-performance-bio-based-and-hybrid-coatings>

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

TEXTILES IN TRANSITION – FASHION.ED FINAL CONFERENCE (16 SEPTEMBER 2025)

PROPLANET was presented at the [Textiles in Transition – Fashion.ED Final Conference](#), where partners participated in discussions on sustainable transformation in the textile sector. The event enabled the exchange of insights on innovation, circularity, and safer material solutions, while highlighting PROPLANET's contribution to advancing sustainable coatings and SSbD approaches within textile value chains.

INTEGRANO WORKSHOP – SSbD: BOOSTING SUSTAINABILITY AND SAFETY IN THE TEXTILE SECTOR (25 SEPTEMBER 2025)

PROPLANET took part in the [INTEGRANO workshop](#) focused on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) in the textile sector. During the workshop, the project's activities and methodological approaches were presented, contributing to discussions on improving sustainability, safety, and regulatory alignment in textile applications. The event fostered dialogue with other EU initiatives and reinforced the relevance of SSbD principles in industrial practice.

PROPLANET AT THE ZEROF PROJECT EVENT (20 NOVEMBER 2025)

The **ZeroF Project Event** successfully concluded on **20 November 2025** in **Barcelona**, hosted at the **Leitat Technological Center**. The event brought together experts and stakeholders to focus on **innovation and sustainability** in chemical and material solutions.

The **PROPLANET Project** participated actively, with **Dr. Òscar Calvo i Mezquida** from **AITEX** representing the project during a dynamic panel discussion. He shared insights on **PFAS-free solutions** and the future development of **safe and sustainable coatings**, highlighting the role of digital tools and SSbD principles in advancing greener materials.

The event fostered **collaboration and knowledge exchange** across projects and participants, reinforcing efforts toward a PFAS-free future. PROPLANET extended thanks to the **ZeroF team** and all participants for their contributions and engagement.

The agenda was announced here:

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/zerof-project_zerof-final-event-activity-7396082661414342656-xgoU?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAABMJMcBeD3HbQbMchyXYCfi8szLwM5BqSY

SSbD EVENTS IN BRUSSELS (19-20 MARCH)

TEXTILES IN TRANSITION – FASHION.ED FINAL CONFERENCE (16 SEPTEMBER 2025)

The **PROPLANET Project**, represented by **IDENER.AI**, participated in two key **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)** events held in Brussels on **19–20 March**.

On the first day, PROPLANET contributed to the **6th SSbD Stakeholder Event**, organised by **DG RTD** under the theme “Safe and Sustainable by Design: Accelerating the Industrial Transition”. This hybrid event brought together policymakers, industry representatives, and research organisations to support Europe’s transition towards safer and more sustainable chemicals. PROPLANET participated in the discussions and presented its work, contributing to the broader dialogue on SSbD implementation.

On the second day, PROPLANET took part in an **in person networking event** with other EU funded projects, the European Commission, **HaDEA**, and **REA**. The meeting focused on identifying opportunities for collaboration and strengthening synergies to support the industrial transition towards safe and sustainable chemical solutions.

SSbD Event – Networking of Horizon Europe Projects

Brussels, 20 March 2026

PROPLANET FINAL EVENT AT COATINGS 2026

Coatings
2026
Conference

Coatings 2026: Safe and Sustainable by Design Surface Treatment and Coatings

20–22 April 2026 | Athens, Greece

The [COATINGS 2026 Conference](#), jointly organised by **EXELISIS** and **MDPI**, successfully served as the final dissemination event of the PROPLANET project and provided a shared platform for knowledge exchange with related EU funded initiatives, including FreeMe, MOZART, and CoBrain. The conference brought together researchers, industry representatives, policymakers, and innovation stakeholders to discuss advances and future directions in coatings science, sustainable materials, and high performance surface technologies.

The event attracted over 120 participants and featured more than 50 oral talks and more than 50 poster presentations, demonstrating strong engagement from the coatings community. The programme comprised [ten thematic sessions](#) covering a broad range of topics, from metallic, organic, and hybrid coatings to SSbD implementation, AI tools, and the phasing out of substances of concern, offering a comprehensive overview of current research and industrial challenges.

PROPLANET partners actively contributed to the conference with **two oral and three poster presentations**, showcasing key project results and fostering exchange with the wider community. In particular, the following works were shared with the conference participants.

Oral talks:

- **Fabiola Brusciotti (TECNALIA):**
PFAS-free sol-gel hybrid coatings for sustainable cookware, glass and food-packaging equipment
- **Johannes Peter Seif (IDENER):**
Digital Innovation for PFAS-free Coating Development: The PROPLANET Replication Tool

Poster presentations:

- **Ioanna Katsavou (EXELISIS):**
Assessing Market Readiness and Business Models for PFAS-Free SSbD Coating Solutions
- **Eleonora Marta Longhin (NILU):**
Tiered Hazard Assessment Implementing New Approach Methodologies for PFAS-Free Coatings in a Safe and Sustainable by Design Context
- **Antonio Borrego Ortega (UMA):**
Multiobjective optimisation framework for the sustainable-by-design assessment of industrial coating production processes

Plenary and invited speakers further enriched the programme by providing high level insights into emerging trends and strategic priorities. Networking activities, including poster sessions and social events, played a key role in strengthening collaborations and supporting knowledge exchange across projects and sectors.

PROPLANET'S FUN CORNER

As part of its commitment to **raising awareness about sustainability and the impact of chemicals on our planet**, the **PROPLANET Project** produced a special **kids' magazine** aimed at inspiring the next generation of young scientists and environmentally conscious citizens. The publication was designed to make complex topics accessible and engaging, helping children understand how **safe and sustainable materials** can contribute to a healthier world.

The magazine featured a variety of **fun activities, games, puzzles, and illustrations**, all centred around key themes such as **coatings, materials science, environmental protection, and the importance of choosing PFAS free solutions**. Through interactive content, young readers were encouraged to explore ideas like **how materials affect our planet, how scientists work to reduce environmental risks, and what it means to design safer products for the future**.

The magazine was freely available for download and distribution, inviting classrooms, families, and community groups to join PROPLANET's mission and help foster **a generation that cares about sustainable materials and the future of our planet**.

Take a look on the Kids Flyer in English:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/PROPLANET-Flyer-A4-ENG.pdf>

And in Greek:

<https://www.proplanet-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/PROPLANET-Flyer-A4-Greek-2.pdf>

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